

EFFECT OF NON-METALLIC INCLUSIONS

ON AISI 4140 FATIGUE STRENGTH

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ABSTRACT

In the present paper, a procedure for fatigue strength assessment of high strength steels (AISI 4140) containing non-metallic inclusions (NMIs) is proposed. Such a procedure implements: (i) a defect content analysis, (ii) the $\sqrt{\text{area}}$ -parameter model, and (iii) the multiaxial critical plane-based criterion by Carpinteri et al. According to the defect content analysis, the distribution of NMIs is determined in two cross-sections perpendicular to the maximum principal stress directions under normal and shear uniaxial cyclic loadings. The return periods, obtained optimising the accuracy of the procedure in terms of fatigue strength estimation, are determined by taking into account five different control volumes. The results achieved through the proposed procedure are compared with both the experimental data and the results obtained employing the Carpinteri et al. criterion without optimisation.

KEYWORDS: critical plane-based criterion; extreme value theory; fatigue limit; infinite fatigue life; non-metallic inclusions

1. INTRODUCTION

Non-metallic inclusions (NMIs), which are chemical compounds of metals with non-metals, are inevitably formed during most metallurgical processes involving steel in a liquid state, due to the presence of dissolved oxygen and other exogenous materials [1]. Such inclusions are usually classified according to their chemical composition (such as oxides, sulfides, aluminates and silicates), their size (micro- or macro-inclusions) or by considering the moment of their formation with respect to the beginning of the solidification process [1,2]. Moreover, they could be endogenous if originating from the steelmaking process or exogenous if appearing as a consequence of external sources (such as fragments of refractories, entrapped slag and oxidation in air when the molten steel is poured without isolation from the environment) [3].

Many efforts has been made over the years to investigate and control the effects of such inclusions in steel. Even if NMIs typically occur in a low or very low volume fraction, they significantly influence the properties of the metallic materials containing them [3]. As a matter of fact, there always exists a large number of NMIs in steels, and they can affect the material fatigue properties. The effects of type, composition, shape and size of such inclusions have been discussed in several publications [4-9]. However, among the different aspects (such as size, shape, adhesion to matrix, thermal and elastic properties), the inclusion size has the major effect on the fatigue strength [4,8,9]. Moreover, it is worth noting that NMIs do not only cause a reduction in fatigue

strength of steels, which is more relevant in hard steels, but they also cause a considerable scatter in fatigue data [6].

Several Authors [10-14] have observed that NMIs are one of the leading causes of failures reported in the literature, regarding gearboxes, pipelines, railway wheels, crankshafts and so on. For instance, it has been experimentally observed that the failure of bearings in wind turbine gearbox is often associated with the occurrence of White Etching Cracks (WECs), where the crack initiation sites are in correspondence of non-metallic inclusions produced during the steel manufacturing process [13,14]. Also in railway wheels subjected to rolling contact fatigue (caused by the cyclic rolling contact with the rails), fatigue cracks may initiate and propagate from internal defects, such as non-metallic inclusions, that exist below the wheel tread surface [15-19]. Moreover, several research studies have shown that the crankshaft fatigue failures are usually characterised by cracks initiating from non-metallic inclusions [20-24].

Further, from a careful review of the literature, it can be observed that NMIs affect both short and long lifetimes of high strength steels [25-27]. Therefore, it is important to consider their influence in estimating the fatigue lifetime. In such a context, Machado et al. [28] proposed to use a classical critical plane-based criterion in conjunction with the \sqrt{area} -parameter model proposed by Murakami [29] and Yanase et al. [30].

Murakami et al. [31] performed rotating bending fatigue tests on specimens made of two types of steel, where small artificial holes

with different diameters were machined. They observed that the fatigue strength did not decrease if non-damaging defects were present, revealing the existence of a critical defect size which was crucial to determine the fatigue strength, mainly in high strength steels [31,32]. More precisely, fatigue problem involving components with small defects could be treated as short crack problems, where the fatigue strength had a strong correlation with the square root of the cracked area, \sqrt{area} [33]. As far as non-metallic inclusions are concerned, it was observed that fatigue crack usually nucleated at the interface between the inclusion and the matrix and/or the inclusion itself was cracked. Consequently, the stress within the inclusion was relieved, and the inclusion could be regarded as mechanically equivalent to a small defect [29].

Such an aspect is typical of high strength steels, where the sizes of the inclusions are greater than a critical value. Therefore, fatigue limits under axial loading or torsion loading may be estimated through the formulations proposed by Murakami [29] and Yanase et al. [30], respectively, both involving \sqrt{area} . Moreover, since inclusions are more than a single one, a statistical distribution of them is needed, by assuming that: (a) the inclusion with the maximum area, $area_{max}$, contained in the selected cross-section of the specimen, is expected to become the fatigue fracture origin, and (b) such an inclusion is just below the cross-section surface.

The present paper aims to theoretically investigate the fatigue behaviour of an AISI 4140 steel containing NMIs. In particular,

infinite life fatigue tests, available in the literature [28] and related to both uniaxial and biaxial cyclic loading, are hereafter simulated. A procedure for fatigue strength assessment is adopted, by implementing (i) a defect content analysis, (ii) the $\sqrt{\text{area}}$ -parameter model [29,30], and (iii) the multiaxial critical plane-based criterion by Carpinteri et al. [34-39]. Although the above tests have already been simulated in Ref. [40], the novelties of the present work consist in: (i) a defect content analysis performed by employing all the experimental data reported in Ref. [28]; (ii) a different approach to optimise the accuracy of the procedure; (iii) a different set of data employed to perform the optimisation, more representative of the fatigue phenomenon.

The manuscript is structured as follows. In **Section 2**, the framework of the procedure for fatigue strength assessment is presented. The experimental campaign examined, performed on an AISI 4140 steel under uniaxial and multiaxial fatigue loading, is described in detail in **Section 3**. In **Section 4**, the procedure is applied to the above experimental test data, whereas the results obtained are discussed in **Section 5**. Finally, the main relevant conclusions are reported in **Section 6**.

2. A PROCEDURE FOR FATIGUE STRENGTH ASSESSMENT OF METALS WITH NON-METALLIC INCLUSIONS

The procedure here used is briefly summarised in the flowchart shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1.

As can be noted, the procedure implements:

- (i) a defect content analysis, performed according to the extreme value theory [41,42];
- (ii) the \sqrt{area} -parameter model [29,30];
- (iii) the multiaxial critical plane-based criterion by Carpinteri et al. [34-39].

Firstly, the algorithm requires some *input data* related to:

- the applied loading conditions, that is: the ranges of both the normal, $\Delta\sigma$, and shear, $\Delta\tau$, stresses applied to the specimen, the phase shift, β , between the normal stress and the shear stress and the loading ratio, R ;
- the mechanical properties of the material, that is: the ultimate tensile strength, σ_u , and the Vickers hardness, HV ;
- and, according to the extreme value theory, the values of $V_{0,n}$, $V_{0,s}$, V and V_{max} , that are the standard inspection volumes related to normal and shear stress uniaxial loading, the volume of the useful cross-section and the maximum value of the useful cross-section volume, respectively.

The *defect content analysis* (red box in **Figure 1**) is performed according to the extreme value theory, and requires that both the distribution of defects and the return periods are determined [41,42]. In general, it is carried out by examining the fracture surface of specimens under both normal and shear uniaxial cyclic loading, in order to define $\sqrt{area_{n\ max}}$ and $\sqrt{area_{s\ max}}$ for each loading condition (that is, the square root of the expected maximum size of

the defects related to normal and shear uniaxial cyclic loading, respectively).

Once $\sqrt{area_{n_{max}}}$ and $\sqrt{area_{s_{max}}}$ are computed, the material *fatigue limits under normal loading*, σ_w , and *shear loading*, τ_w , are calculated by means of the \sqrt{area} -parameter model [29,30] (blue box in **Figure 1**).

In particular, under normal cyclic loading, the value of σ_w is calculated as a function of both the material Vickers hardness, HV , and the parameter $\sqrt{area_{n_{max}}}$, as suggested by Murakami [41,42]:

$$\sigma_w = \frac{1.41(HV + 120)}{(\sqrt{area_{n_{max}}})^{1/6}} \quad (1)$$

Note that the above equation is related to a defect just below the cross-section surface and corresponding to a number of loading cycle equal to $1 \cdot (10)^7$ [29].

Analogously, a similar relationship for the computation of the fatigue limit under shear loading, τ_w , was proposed by Yanase et al. [30]:

$$\tau_w = \frac{1.19(HV + 120)}{(\sqrt{area_{s_{max}}})^{1/6}} \quad (2)$$

Once the fatigue limits are computed, the *fatigue strength assessment of the material* is performed through the Carpinteri et al. criterion [34-39] (grey box in **Figure 1**).

More precisely, firstly the orientation of the critical plane (that is, the verification plane where the fatigue strength is performed) is determined by means of an off-angle δ formed by the normal to the critical plane and the averaged direction of the maximum principal stress, according to the following equation:

$$\delta = \frac{3\pi}{8} \left[1 - \left(\frac{\tau_w}{\sigma_w} \right)^2 \right] \quad (3)$$

The fatigue limits σ_w (**Eq. (1)**) and τ_w (**Eq. (2)**) respectively replace the experimental fatigue strengths (at a given number of loading cycles) for fully reversed normal stress, $\sigma_{af,-1}$, and for fully reversed shear stress, $\tau_{af,-1}$, employed in the original version of the Carpinteri et al. criterion **[34-39]**.

Then, an equivalent uniaxial stress, $\sigma_{eq,a}$, is equated to the amplitude of the normal fatigue strength, σ_w , in order to impose the fatigue endurance condition:

$$\sigma_{eq,a} = \sqrt{N_{eq,a}^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_w}{\tau_w} \right)^2} C_a^2 = \sigma_w \quad (4)$$

with:

$$N_{eq,a} = N_a + \sigma_w \left(\frac{N_m}{\sigma_u} \right) \quad (5)$$

N_a and N_m are the amplitude and the mean value, respectively, of the normal component, \mathbf{N} , of the stress vector, \mathbf{S}_w , on the critical plane, whereas C_a is the amplitude of the shear component, \mathbf{C} , of \mathbf{S}_w . To interested readers, details may be found in Refs **[34-39]**.

Finally, an error index, I , used to evaluate the accuracy of the proposed procedure, is computed for each experimental test examined:

$$I = \frac{\sigma_{eq,a} - \sigma_w}{\sigma_w} \cdot 100 \quad (6)$$

3. THE EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN EXAMINED

The procedure presented in the previous Section is hereafter employed to simulate an experimental campaign available in the literature [28]. The examined material was a high strength AISI 4140 steel, oil quenched and tempered at 600°C, extracted from a broken crankshaft of a power plant engine that failed during service. In particular, smooth specimens with a diameter equal to 10mm in the gauge section and designed according to ASTM E466-15 standard [43] were tested. To avoid any possible surface defects, the specimens were finally polished with sandpaper to a final roughness lower than 3µm.

The AISI 4140 steel mechanical properties are as follows [28]: yield strength equal to 710 MPa, ultimate tensile strength equal to 900 MPa, elongation at failure equal to 20% and Vickers Hardness equal to 320.

The experimental campaign consisted of both uniaxial (tension or torsion) and biaxial (combined tension and torsion) fatigue tests performed under load control by means of a servo-hydraulic axial-torsional fatigue testing machine (100 kN and 1100 Nm load capacity, respectively) in accordance with the ASTM E466-15 standard [43]. Fully reversed sinusoidal signals were considered (i.e. with loading ratio $R=-1$) and the test frequencies ranged between 5 and 15 Hz.

The specimen complete rupture was used as the failure criterion, whereas the run-out condition was assumed in correspondence of $2 \cdot (10)^6$ loading cycles.

The experimental fully reversed normal and shear fatigue limits were computed as $\sigma_{af,-1} = 375 \text{ MPa}$ and $\tau_{af,-1} = 282 \text{ MPa}$, respectively, through a modified version of the staircase method. Thus, under uniaxial loading, the S-N (normal stress against number of loading cycles) and T-N (shear stress against number of loading cycles) curves were generated, whose expressions are here reported [28]:

$$S = 1202N^{-0.083} \quad (7)$$

$$T = 679N^{-0.062} \quad (8)$$

As far as the multiaxial fatigue tests are concerned, five different ratios between shear stress amplitude $\tau_{xy,a}$ and normal stress amplitude $\sigma_{x,a}$ were adopted, and more precisely: (a) 0.0, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0 and ∞ with a phase shift β equal to 0° , and (b) 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0 with a phase shift $\beta = 90^\circ$.

The fatigue data related to the experimental campaign examined [28] are listed in **Table 1**.

Finally, two specimens were chosen to perform the defect content analyses. More precisely, two cross-sections were examined: one perpendicular to the specimen longitudinal axis (which represents the direction of the maximum principal stress under fully reversed axial loading); and the other one forming 45° with the same axis

(that is, a cross-section normal to the direction of the maximum principal stress under fully reversed shear loading).

After mirror-finishing them with alumina 0.3 μm , each cross-section was observed by a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM, JEOL JSM-7100F) with an inspection area equal to 0.41mm^2 (which was approximately the size of the picture taken by the microscope). In each examined area by the SEM, the biggest inclusion was selected and measured by considering a smooth contour line around the inclusion. Such an operation was repeated 60 times in areas close to the surface edge.

At the end of this procedure, the values of $\sqrt{\text{area}_n}_j$ and $\sqrt{\text{area}_s}_j$ with $j=1,\dots,60$, related to the cross-sections perpendicular to and forming 45° with the specimen longitudinal axis, respectively, are determined.

4. PROCEDURE APPLICATION

The experimental data described in the above Section are hereafter analysed by means of the procedure presented in **Section 2** to perform the fatigue assessment.

4.1 Defect distributions

The defect content analysis is performed according to the extreme value theory [41,42], by employing all the experimental values of $\sqrt{\text{area}_n}_j$ and $\sqrt{\text{area}_s}_j$ available in Ref. [28]. This is the first novelty of the present paper: as a matter of fact, the results reported in Ref. [40] in terms of defect distributions, are taken, without

further elaboration, from Refs [28], where they are obtained by considering only some of the $\sqrt{area_{n_j}}$ and $\sqrt{area_{s_j}}$ measured values.

On the contrary, here, all the experimental $\sqrt{area_{n_j}}$ and $\sqrt{area_{s_j}}$ values are listed in ascending order, both indexed with $j=1,\dots,n$, being n the number of the examined areas close to the surface of the specimen (i.e. $n=60$):

$$\sqrt{area_{n_1}} \leq \sqrt{area_{n_2}} \leq \dots \leq \sqrt{area_{n_{60}}} \quad (9a)$$

$$\sqrt{area_{s_1}} \leq \sqrt{area_{s_2}} \leq \dots \leq \sqrt{area_{s_{60}}} \quad (9b)$$

Then, the reduced variable, y_j , is calculated by means of the following equation for both defect distributions:

$$y_j = -\ln \left[-\ln \left(\frac{j}{n+1} \right) \right] \quad (10)$$

The probability graphs of the defect distributions are plotted in **Figure 2** for both cross-sections, being the y_j values reported on the ordinate axis, and the $\sqrt{area_{n_j}}$ and $\sqrt{area_{s_j}}$ values on the abscissa axes (**Figure 2(a)** and **(b)**, respectively).

Figure 2.

It is interesting to observe that, in both **Figures 2(a)** and **2(b)**, the reduced variable y_j against the $\sqrt{area_j}$ has a linear trend, that is, the points follow a Gumbel distribution. The linear regressions

of the above two defect distributions are given by the following equations:

$$\sqrt{area_{n_{max}}} = \frac{1}{0.0819} y_n + \frac{0.9986}{0.0819} \quad (11a)$$

$$\sqrt{area_{s_{max}}} = \frac{1}{0.0818} y_s + \frac{1.0884}{0.0818} \quad (11b)$$

with:

$$y_n = -\ln \left[-\ln \left(\frac{T_n - 1}{T_n} \right) \right] \quad (12a)$$

$$y_s = -\ln \left[-\ln \left(\frac{T_s - 1}{T_s} \right) \right] \quad (12b)$$

being T_n and T_s the return periods related to normal and shear uniaxial cyclic loadings, respectively.

From **Eqs (11) and (12)**, it can be noted that the $\sqrt{area_{n_{max}}}$ and $\sqrt{area_{s_{max}}}$ values are function of the return periods, T_n and T_s , respectively, depending on the volumes considered in the defect content analysis. In fact, the probability of finding larger defects increases within the volume.

The return periods, T_n and T_s , are defined as the ratios of two volumes, and more precisely:

$$T_n = \frac{V}{V_{0,n}} \quad V = T_n \cdot V_{0,n} \quad (13a)$$

$$T_s = \frac{V}{V_{0,s}} = T_n \frac{V_{0,n}}{V_{0,s}} \quad (13b)$$

where V is the volume of the useful cross-section (*prediction volume*), whereas $V_{0,n}$ and $V_{0,s}$ are the standard inspection volumes related to normal and shear stress uniaxial loading, respectively.

Note that the useful cross-section volume, V , is usually set equal to the volume of the specimen gauge region, whereas the standard inspection volumes are computed by assuming a given thickness associated to the inspection area, S_0 [41,42]. More precisely, the standard inspection volumes are defined as follows:

$$V_{0,n} = S_0 h_n \quad (14a)$$

$$V_{0,s} = S_0 h_s \quad (14b)$$

with:

$$h_n = \frac{\sum_j^n \sqrt{area_{n_j}}}{n} \quad (15a)$$

$$h_s = \frac{\sum_j^n \sqrt{area_{s_j}}}{n} \quad (15b)$$

Once T_n and T_s are computed, the $\sqrt{area_{n_{max}}}$ and $\sqrt{area_{s_{max}}}$ values are determined by employing **Eqs (11)** and **(12)**.

In the present study, the following values of the standard inspection volume are obtained: $V_{0,n} = 6.17 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^3$ and $V_{0,s} = 6.43 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^3$, being $h_n = 18.9 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ and $h_s = 20.0 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$, respectively, for an inspection area S_0 equal to 0.41 mm^2 [28].

Regarding the useful cross-section volume, V , different values are considered in order to optimise the accuracy of the procedure in terms of fatigue strength estimation, as described hereafter. In particular, in the present work, the values of V considered for such an optimisation are different from those employed in Ref. [40], being the present values more representative of the volumes involved in the fatigue phenomenon. Moreover, such an optimisation procedure

is performed with respect to the return period, whereas it was performed with respect to σ_w in Ref. [40].

4.2 Optimised return period

The first two pairs (T_n, T_s) are derived from the experimental data reported in Ref. [28]. More precisely, by alternatively considering the two experimental fatigue strengths, that is, $\sigma_{af,-1}=375MPa$ and $\tau_{af,-1}=282MPa$ at $2 \cdot (10)^6$ loading cycles, two fictitious prediction volumes, $V_{\sigma_{af,-1}}=0.13 mm^3$ and $V_{\tau_{af,-1}}=1.24 mm^3$, and the corresponding return periods values (listed in **Table 2**), are determined.

Table 2.

Then, three other values of the prediction volume are assumed and the corresponding values of T_n and T_s are computed (see **Table 2**), that is: (i) the volume of the specimen gauge section $V_{gauge}=2.40 \cdot 10^3 mm^3$ for which the return periods are $T_n=3.09 \cdot 10^5$ and $T_s=2.92 \cdot 10^5$; (ii) the volume of the whole specimen $V_{spec}=1.73 \cdot 10^4 mm^3$ for which the return periods are $T_n=2.23 \cdot 10^6$ and $T_s=2.11 \cdot 10^6$; (iii) the volume of the whole crankshaft $V_{crank}=7.90 \cdot 10^9 mm^3$ for which the return periods are $T_n=1.02 \cdot 10^{12}$ and $T_s=9.61 \cdot 10^{11}$.

Then, for each of the above pairs of values (T_n, T_s) , the fatigue limits σ_w and τ_w are computed through **Eqs (1)** and **(2)**. Note that,

the run-out condition in the experimental campaign examined was taken in correspondence of $2 \cdot (10)^6$ loading cycles, while the fatigue limits obtained by employing **Eqs (1) and (2)** correspond to a number of loading cycles equal to $1 \cdot (10)^7$ (according to Murakami and Yanase proposals). Therefore, the same slopes of the experimental S-N and T-N curves reported in **Eqs (7) and (8)** are respectively employed to compute the values of σ_w and τ_w corresponding to $2 \cdot (10)^6$ loading cycles and such values are listed in **Table 2**.

The algorithm block named Carpinteri et al. criterion in **Figure 1**, is executed and the corresponding mean value of the error index, \bar{I} , is determined, for each of the above pairs of values (σ_w, τ_w) . According to the framework of the procedure shown in **Figure 1**, the maximum value of V adopted is $V_{max} = V_{crank} = 7.90 \cdot 10^9 \text{ mm}^3$.

Therefore, the mean value of the error index, \bar{I} , is plotted against the return period T_n in **Figure 3** in a semi-logarithmic scale (equivalently the return period T_s may be used in place of T_n).

Figure 3.

Such points are interpolated by means of a logarithmic curve and the following relationship is obtained (R-squared = 0.939):

$$\bar{I}(T_n) = 1.375 \ln(T_n) - 12.455 \quad (16)$$

From **Eq. (16)**, it is possible to derive the value of T_n for which $\bar{I} = 0$, i.e. $T_{n,opt} = 8.59 \cdot 10^3$, which corresponds to a useful cross-section

volume $V_{opt} = 66.64 \text{ mm}^3$ and to a return period $T_{s,opt} = 8.11 \cdot 10^3$.

Consequently, by exploiting **Eqs (11)** and **(12)**, the values of $\sqrt{area_n}_{max} = 122.79 \mu\text{m}$ and $\sqrt{area_s}_{max} = 123.34 \mu\text{m}$ are computed, and the corresponding fatigue limits at $2 \cdot (10)^6$ loading cycles, σ_w and τ_w , are computed (see **Table 2**).

Finally, the algorithm block named Carpinteri et al. criterion in **Figure 1** is executed for the last time.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The uniaxial and the biaxial fatigue data related to the AISI 4140 steel [28] are here analysed and, in order to validate the accuracy of the *proposed procedure*, the present results are compared to those obtained by applying:

- *Method A*: the Carpinteri et al. criterion directly to the data presented in Ref. [28] (that is, the experimental fatigue strengths $\sigma_w = \sigma_{af,-1} = 375 \text{ MPa}$ $\tau_w = \tau_{af,-1} = 282 \text{ MPa}$ are employed);
- *Method B*: the Carpinteri et al. criterion by employing the fatigue strengths, $\sigma_w = 302.29 \text{ MPa}$ and $\tau_w = 246.50 \text{ MPa}$, computed by using the specimen gauge volume $V_{gauge} = 2.40 \cdot 10^3 \text{ mm}^3$ (that is, the useful cross-section volume adopted in Ref. [28]).

The results in terms of stress components on the critical plane (i.e. $N_{eq,a}$ and C_a) are listed in **Table 3** for all the loading conditions. Note that, for experimental tests performed at the same

stress level (for instance, tests Nos 1 and 2), the present procedure is able to provide only one pair of values $N_{eq,a}-C_a$.

Table 3.

Therefore, the above results in terms of stress components are plotted in **Figures 4, 5** and **6** for all data being examined (that is, each point corresponds to a given experimental test). In particular, the results obtained applying the proposed procedure are plotted in **Figure 4**; those by *Method A* in **Figure 5** and, finally, those by *Method B* in **Figure 6**.

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

In such figures, the fatigue endurance condition, given by **Eq. (4)**, defines an ellipse with the semi-axes equal to σ_w along the abscissa axis and to τ_w along the ordinate axis. The dashed lines in such Figures correspond to an error band equal to $\pm 10\%$, whereas the dash-dot lines to an error band equal to $\pm 20\%$. The full symbols refer to specimens that failed, whereas the empty ones refer to run-outs. Moreover, empty symbols in red represent loading conditions in

correspondence of which both failure and run-out were experimentally observed.

It is worth noting that, if a given $N_{eq,a}-C_a$ point lies inside the above ellipses, a run-out condition is predicted; whereas fatigue failure is estimated if the point is outside the elliptical domain. Moreover, if both run-out and failure conditions were experimentally observed (see for instance tests Nos 7-8 in **Table 1**), only one of the above conditions could be provided. In particular, in order to obtain conservative results, the fatigue failure condition should be estimated.

As far as uniaxial fatigue data are concerned, the following remarks can be made:

- for tensile fatigue loading, the experimental failures (tests Nos 7-8 and 9-10) are correctly predicted by the *present procedure*, whereas all the run-outs (tests Nos 1-2, 3-4 and 5-6) are predicted as failures even if they fall inside the scatter band +20% (**Figure 4(a)**); moreover, the results determined through *Method A* are less conservative, falling tests Nos 7-8 in the safe domain (**see Figure 5(a)**), whereas those obtained through *Method B* are more conservative (**Figure 6(a)**);

- for torsional fatigue loading, the *procedure* perfectly estimates both the fatigue failures for tests Nos 19-20 and No. 21, the run-out conditions for tests Nos 11-12, 13-14 and 15-16 and even the condition of incipient failure for tests Nos 17-18 (that is, the corresponding $N_{eq,a}-C_a$ point lies very close to the failure curve) when both failure and run-out condition are observed (**Figure 4(a)**),

in agreement with the experimental outcomes; moreover, the results obtained through *Method A* are less conservative, falling test No. 18 in the safe domain (see red symbol in **Figure 5(a)**), whereas those obtained through *Method B* are more conservative (**Figure 6(a)**).

Regarding to biaxial fatigue, it can be observed that:

- for in-phase loading, the *present procedure* allows to correctly estimate the failure of tests Nos 24, 25-26, 30 and 33-34 and the run-out tests No. 27, whereas the run-out conditions of tests Nos 22, 28-29 and 31-32 are predicted as incipient failures, lying the points on the ellipse (**Figure 4(a)**); the results obtained through *Method A* are non-conservative, falling all the points in the safe domain (**Figure 5(a)**), whereas those obtained through *Method B* are more conservative, predicting the failure of all specimens (**Figure 6(a)**).

- for out-of-phase loading, the *present procedure* correctly predicts the failure of tests Nos 40-41 and 42-43 ($\tau_{xy,a}/\sigma_{x,a}=0.5$), the run-out conditions for tests Nos 35, 36 and 37 ($\tau_{xy,a}/\sigma_{x,a}=1.0$) and for tests Nos 44 and 45 ($\tau_{xy,a}/\sigma_{x,a}=2.0$), and the incipient failure for tests No. 46 ($\tau_{xy,a}/\sigma_{x,a}=2.0$) (**Figure 4(b)**). On the contrary, such a *procedure* is not able to predict the failure of test Nos 38-39 ($\tau_{xy,a}/\sigma_{x,a}=1.0$), even if the point falls in the scatter band -20% (**Figure 4(b)**). Moreover, the results through *Method A* are non-conservative, falling all the points in the safe domain (**Figure 5(b)**), whereas those through *Method B* are quite similar to those through the *present procedure* (**Figure 6(b)**).

In general, we can conclude that the *procedure* is able to correctly estimate the fatigue strength with a good accuracy, since it provides non-conservative results only for tests Nos 38-39.

Let us now consider only the tests that experiment failure (see **Table 1**). For such tests, only the equivalent stress amplitude computed according to both the *present procedure* and the *Carpinteri et al. criterion* by employing the experimental values of fatigue strengths (*Method A* in the above discussion) is reported in **Table 4** and plotted in **Figure 7**.

Table 4.

Figure 7

The horizontal thick red lines represent the fatigue limit $\sigma_w = 318.05 \text{ MPa}$ in **Figure 7(a)** and the fatigue limit under fully reversed normal stress $\sigma_{af,-1} = 375 \text{ MPa}$ in **Figure 7(b)**. It can be observed that, when the *present procedure* is applied to the experimental data, 92% of the fatigue strength estimations are conservative (**Figure 7(a)**), whereas only the 15% of the estimations are conservative when the *Carpinteri et al. criterion* is applied (**Figure 7(b)**). Such a result shows an improvement in terms of procedure accuracy with respect to that of the procedure employed in Ref. [40], where the 85% of the fatigue strength estimations were conservative.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, the fatigue behaviour of a high strength steel (AISI 4140) containing non-metallic inclusions (NMIs) has been analysed by using a fatigue strength assessment procedure, implementing: (i) a defect content analysis, (ii) the \sqrt{area} -parameter model, and (iii) the multiaxial critical plane-based criterion by Carpinteri et al.

The defect content analysis on the experimental data has been performed according to the extreme value theory and by considering two cross-sections perpendicular to the maximum principal stress directions under normal and shear uniaxial cyclic loadings. For each cross-section, the values $\sqrt{area_{n_{max}}}$ and $\sqrt{area_{s_{max}}}$ are determined together with the corresponding return periods for five control volumes. Then, an optimised return period, T_n , for which the error index average value is equal to zero, is determined and used to compute the fatigue limits under normal and shear loadings.

The fatigue strength assessment of the AISI 4140 steel is performed, showing a quite accurate estimation of experimental failure and run-out. More precisely, according to the present procedure, the fatigue strength estimation is more conservative (in favour of safety) with respect to that predicted by the Carpinteri et al. criterion.

In conclusion, the present procedure implementing an optimised computation of the return period has shown to be able to correctly estimate the fatigue strength of steels with NMIs, representing a useful tool in fatigue design of real components. As a matter of

fact, it can be applied also in presence of other type of defects, such as micro-shrinkage porosity usually present, for example, in ductile cast iron.

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NOMENCLATURE

$\sqrt{area_n}_{max}$	square root of the expected maximum size of the NMIs in the cross-section perpendicular to the specimen longitudinal axis
$\sqrt{area_s}_{max}$	square root of the expected maximum size of the NMIs in the cross-section forming 45° with the specimen longitudinal axis
C_a	amplitude of the shear stress component on the critical plane
h_n and h_s	thickness associated to the inspection area in the two cross-sections
HV	Vickers hardness
I	error index
N_a	amplitude of the normal stress component perpendicular to the critical plane
$N_{eq,a}$	equivalent normal stress amplitude
N_{exp}	experimental number of loading cycles to failure
N_m	mean value of the normal stress component perpendicular to the critical plane
R	loading ratio
S_0	inspection area
\mathbf{S}_w	stress vector on the critical plane
T_n and T_s	return periods associated to the two cross-sections
$T_{n,opt}$	optimised return period related to the cross-section perpendicular to the specimen longitudinal axis
V	useful cross-section volume
$V_{0,n}$ and $V_{0,s}$	standard inspection volume associated to the two cross-sections
V_{max}	maximum value of the useful cross-section volume
β	phase shift between normal stress and shear stress
δ	off-angle defining the normal to the critical plane

$\sigma_{x,a}$	applied normal stress amplitude
$\sigma_{af,-1}$	experimental material fatigue strength under fully reversed normal stress
$\sigma_{eq,a}$	equivalent uniaxial stress amplitude
σ_u	material ultimate tensile strength
σ_w	fatigue limit under normal loading
$\tau_{xy,a}$	applied shear stress amplitude
$\tau_{af,-1}$	experimental material fatigue strength under fully reversed shear stress
τ_w	fatigue limit under torsion

EFFECT OF NON-METALLIC INCLUSIONS

ON AISI 4140 FATIGUE STRENGTH

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FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1. Flowchart of the fatigue strength assessment procedure.

Table 1. Fatigue data related to the experimental campaign examined [28].

TEST No.	$\tau_{xy,a}/\sigma_{x,a}$ [-]	β [°]	$\sigma_{x,a}$ [MPa]	$\tau_{xy,a}$ [MPa]	$N_{f,exp}$ [cycles]	
1-2	0	-	345	-	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
3-4	0	-	360	-	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
5-6	0	-	375	-	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
7	0	-	390	-	$5.85 \cdot 10^5$	Failed
8	0	-	390	-	$4.23 \cdot 10^5$	Failed
9	0	-	314	-	$3.38 \cdot 10^5$	Failed
10	0	-	314	-	$4.33 \cdot 10^5$	Failed
11-12	∞	-	-	262.5	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
13-14	∞	-	-	275	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
15-16	∞	-	-	280	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
17	∞	-	-	287.5	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
18	∞	-	-	287.5	$8.79 \cdot 10^5$	Failed
19	∞	-	-	300	$3.81 \cdot 10^5$	Failed
20	∞	-	-	300	$1.12 \cdot 10^6$	Failed
21	∞	-	-	321	$2.13 \cdot 10^5$	Failed
22	1.0	0	200	200	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
23	1.0	0	210	210	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
24	1.0	0	210	210	$4.78 \cdot 10^5$	Failed
25	1.0	0	220	220	$3.32 \cdot 10^5$	Failed
26	1.0	0	220	220	$1.36 \cdot 10^6$	Failed
27	0.5	0	260	130	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
28	0.5	0	280	140	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
29	0.5	0	300	150	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
30	0.5	0	300	150	$1.65 \cdot 10^6$	Failed
31-32	2.0	0	120	240	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
33	2.0	0	130	260	$5.35 \cdot 10^5$	Failed
34	2.0	0	130	260	$5.36 \cdot 10^5$	Failed
35	1.0	90	200	200	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
36	1.0	90	210	210	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
37	1.0	90	220	220	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
38	1.0	90	230	230	$7.71 \cdot 10^5$	Failed
39	1.0	90	230	230	$1.65 \cdot 10^6$	Failed
40	0.5	90	300	150	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
41	0.5	90	300	150	$7.34 \cdot 10^5$	Failed
42	0.5	90	320	160	$7.50 \cdot 10^5$	Failed
43	0.5	90	320	160	$3.52 \cdot 10^5$	Failed
44	2.0	90	130	260	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
45	2.0	90	135	270	$2.00 \cdot 10^6$	<i>Run-out</i>
46	2.0	90	140	280	$1.04 \cdot 10^6$	Failed

Figure 2. Probability graphs of the defect distribution, according to the extreme value theory, related to the cross-sections: (a) perpendicular to, and (b) forming 45° with the specimen longitudinal axis.

Table 2. Useful cross-section volume (prediction volume), return periods, fatigue strengths and error index mean value corresponding to the simulations performed.

Prediction volume		T_n	T_s	σ_w	τ_w	\bar{I}
Symbol	Size					
	[mm ³]	[-]	[-]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[%]
$V_{\sigma_{af,-1}}$	0.13	16.06	15.17	375.00	305.49	-12.60
$V_{\tau_{af,-1}}$	1.24	159.41	150.53	346.00	282.00	-5.29
V_{gauge}	$2.40 \cdot 10^3$	$3.09 \cdot 10^5$	$2.92 \cdot 10^5$	302.29	246.5	8.43
V_{spec}	$1.73 \cdot 10^4$	$2.23 \cdot 10^6$	$2.11 \cdot 10^6$	295.55	241.02	10.85
V_{crank}	$7.90 \cdot 10^9$	$1.02 \cdot 10^{12}$	$9.61 \cdot 10^{11}$	267.13	271.87	22.63
V_{opt}	66.64	$8.59 \cdot 10^3$	$8.11 \cdot 10^3$	318.05	259.31	3.01

Figure 3. Error index mean value vs return period T_n .

Table 3. Results in terms of stress components on the critical plane by applying the proposed procedure, *Method A* ($\sigma_w=375 \text{ MPa}$; $\tau_w=282 \text{ MPa}$) and *Method B* ($\sigma_w=302.29 \text{ MPa}$; $\tau_w=246.50 \text{ MPa}$).

TEST No.	<i>Present procedure</i>		<i>Method A</i>		<i>Method B</i>	
	$N_{eq,a}$ [MPa]	C_a [MPa]	$N_{eq,a}$ [MPa]	C_a [MPa]	$N_{eq,a}$ [MPa]	C_a [MPa]
1-2	293.87	122.64	262.18	147.40	293.94	122.58
3-4	306.65	127.96	273.58	153.80	306.72	127.90
5-6	319.43	133.29	284.98	160.21	319.50	138.55
7-8	332.21	138.62	296.39	166.62	332.28	138.55
9-10	352.66	147.14	314.63	176.86	352.73	147.07
11-12	184.95	186.42	136.74	224.17	185.05	186.33
13-14	193.75	195.30	143.24	234.84	193.85	195.21
15-16	197.27	198.85	145.84	239.11	197.37	198.76
17-18	202.55	204.18	149.74	245.52	202.65	204.08
19-20	211.35	213.06	156.24	256.19	211.46	212.96
21	226.13	227.98	167.16	274.13	226.24	227.86
22	257.47	158.85	216.40	190.98	257.55	158.77
23-24	270.34	166.79	227.22	200.53	270.43	166.71
25-26	283.21	174.73	238.03	210.08	283.30	174.64
27	259.45	130.64	225.67	157.04	259.50	130.58
28	279.40	140.69	243.03	169.12	279.46	140.62
29-30	299.36	150.73	260.38	181.20	299.42	150.66
31-32	234.24	175.71	188.80	211.27	234.33	175.63
33-34	253.75	190.36	204.53	228.88	253.85	190.26
35	188.68	125.33	159.24	148.38	188.73	125.29
36	198.11	131.60	167.20	155.80	198.16	131.55
37	207.54	137.87	175.16	163.22	207.60	137.82
38-39	216.97	144.13	183.12	170.64	217.03	144.10
40-41	271.22	157.19	252.78	159.79	271.25	157.18
42-43	289.30	167.67	269.63	170.44	289.33	167.66
44	196.66	178.40	150.83	215.48	196.75	178.31
45	204.22	185.26	156.63	223.76	204.32	185.17
46	213.07	193.14	162.43	232.05	211.88	192.03

Figure 4. Shear stress amplitude vs equivalent normal stress amplitude for: (a) in-phase and (b) out-of-phase loading conditions, determined by employing the *present procedure*.

Figure 5. Shear stress amplitude vs equivalent normal stress amplitude for: (a) in-phase and (b) out-of-phase loading conditions obtained, through the Carpinteri et al. criterion by employing the experimental fatigue strength values (*Method A*).

Figure 6. Shear stress amplitude vs equivalent normal stress amplitude for: (a) in-phase and (b) out-of-phase loading conditions, obtained through the Carpinteri et al. criterion by employing the fatigue strength values related to the specimen gauge section volume V_{gauge} (Method B).

Table 4. Results in terms of equivalent stress amplitude computed according to both the *present procedure* and the Carpinteri et al. criterion (*Method A*).

TEST No.	<i>Present procedure</i>	<i>Carpinteri et al. criterion</i>	
	$\sigma_{eq,a}$ [MPa]	$\sigma_{eq,a}$ [MPa]	
7-8	373.19	307.05	Failed
			Failed
9-10	396.15	392.82	Failed
			Failed
18	322.10	359.19	Failed
19-20	336.09	374.80	Failed
			Failed
21	359.62	401.03	Failed
24	339.02	350.33	Failed
25-26	335.16	367.01	Failed
			Failed
30	351.84	354.77	Failed
33-34	344.82	366.69	Failed
			Failed
38-39	279.87	291.57	Failed
			Failed
41	332.76	330.16	Failed
42-43	354.95	352.24	Failed
			Failed
46	318.62	348.71	Failed

Figure 7. Equivalent stress amplitude against the test No., computed according to (a) the *present procedure* and (b) the Carpinteri et al. criterion (*Method A*).